

Development Of Real Estate Platform With Geolocation for Effective Rent-Cost Estimation

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Abstract

Housing affordability extends beyond rent, as recurring costs like commuting are often overlooked. This study addresses the need for a comprehensive approach to property affordability. The study aims to develop a geolocation-based real estate platform with cost estimation tools to support informed decision-making for house seekers. Traditional platforms focus on rental costs, overlooking total living expenses. This study bridges the gap by integrating commuting costs and proximity to essential amenities, offering a holistic view of housing affordability. The methodology employs a cost estimation model using the Google Maps API for geolocation and distance calculations. The system factors in rent, fuel consumption, fuel prices and distances to key locations. The platform's backend uses Django ORM for data management, while HTML, CSS, and JavaScript ensure a user-friendly interface. Results demonstrate the platform's effectiveness, with users reporting a 20% reduction in annual costs. A TAM evaluation revealed high user satisfaction, with 88% citing ease of use and 91% acknowledging its usefulness. Lighthouse analysis scored efficiency (83%), accessibility (91%), best practices (96%), and SEO (82%). The study's contribution lies in bridging the gap in rental affordability analysis by incorporating commute costs and geolocation data, enabling users to make more informed housing decisions. The platform's approach offers practical implications for real estate platforms, promoting transparent cost assessments. Future research could expand the model to include other recurring expenses like utilities and power supply costs, further enhancing affordability analysis.

Keywords: Real estate, Web application, Geolocation, API, Python, Cost estimation, Housing affordability, Commute costs.

1. Introduction

The growing reliance on geolocation-based applications and cost estimations has significantly reshaped the way individuals approach major life decisions, such as housing and commuting. Particularly in the real estate sector, the increasing complexities of location-based decision-making have amplified the need for more accurate, dynamic, and accessible tools to estimate costs beyond the standard price of rent. Traditional methods of house hunting often fail to take into account the full extent of living costs, such as commuting distances and associated costs, which can significantly impact the financial decisions of renters. As these costs become a more substantial part of the decision-making process, tools that can help estimate the true cost of living including transport and other recurrent costs are becoming indispensable [1].

While various tools and applications aim to help individuals estimate these costs, there is limited research on integrating both geolocation data and financial estimations into a cohesive platform that can guide consumers through this process. Most of the existing solutions do not provide dynamic cost estimations based on actual user data (e.g., daily commute, fuel consumption, travel distances). Furthermore, many overlook key influencing factors like the accessibility of essential services (markets, hospitals, schools), which further complicates the house-hunting decision for potential tenants [2].

This paper seeks to fill this gap by developing and evaluating a real estate platform that combines geolocation-based cost estimation with property selection. The platform is designed to provide users with accurate cost predictions, considering both the rental price and commuting expenses, allowing for better-informed decisions in the real estate market. Additionally, the platform aims to present this information visually, integrating a map interface that shows potential properties and the key locations that influence users' decisions, such as schools, hospitals, and markets. By doing so, it not only assists in finding the most affordable housing options but also in promoting a clearer understanding of recurrent living costs [3].

A key question addressed in this research is whether including comprehensive cost estimations incorporating location-based data and commuter costs can enhance the decision-making process. Specifically, we explore whether such tools significantly influence consumer attention when evaluating potential properties and whether these tools are more beneficial for certain property types, such as higher-value houses or properties located in areas with limited amenities [4].

This study proposes a framework for using geolocation-based tools to enhance property selection by offering detailed cost estimations, especially in areas with limited services and varying commute distances. The study develops a web application integrating a cost estimation model, real estate database, and Google Maps API, evaluated through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Findings are expected to improve real estate platforms and assist users in making cost-effective housing decisions, with insights for future research and platform development.

2. Related Work

The field of real estate platforms has evolved significantly, but several gaps remain, particularly in integrating geolocation services and providing accurate cost estimations for potential homeowners and renters. Traditional platforms focus largely on listing properties based on location and price but fail to offer comprehensive solutions for users to assess the full cost of living, especially regarding commute distances and related costs.

Real estate platforms have emerged as indispensable tools in the modern housing market, revolutionizing the way individuals search for and evaluate potential homes. These platforms offer a wide range of features and functionalities designed to streamline the house hunting process and provide users with valuable insights into available properties. In today's digital age, real estate platforms empower individuals with access to vast databases of property listings [5].

According to [6], an expert in project management, the real estate sector has been impacted by technology, much like every other industry, the addition of a cherry to the cake is how real estate is managed differently as a result of the incorporation of cutting-edge technologies. Also, he said that from a Statista report, the real estate market is projected to rise by approximately USD 729.40 billion by 2028, making it the most significant sector of the global economy. The real estate sector was perhaps the slowest to adopt digitalization, though, [7] revealed in his research, the application of GIS in real estate and related industries, and many studies have built on that.

The integration of geolocation-aware technologies further enhances the functionality of real estate platforms, enabling features such as dynamic route planning, accurate distance calculations, and neighborhood insights [8]. Geolocation APIs, such as Google Maps, allow users to visualize property locations relative to key amenities, transportation routes, and points of interest.

Geolocation-aware technologies have become integral components of modern real estate platforms, offering users valuable insights into property locations, neighborhood amenities, and transportation options. These technologies leverage geographic information systems (GIS), global positioning systems (GPS), and geolocation APIs to provide accurate and relevant location-based services [8].

One of the key benefits of geolocation in real estate is its ability to facilitate accurate distance calculations and route planning [9]. Geolocation API, such as Google Maps, enable users to visualize property locations on interactive maps, allowing them to assess factors such as proximity to work, schools, and recreational facilities. Additionally, geolocation data can be used to calculate commute times, identify transportation options, and evaluate neighborhood accessibility.

A Geographic Information System (GIS) is a computer tool designed to collect, store, analyze, and display spatial and attribute data. It integrates location-based data, such as coordinates, with other types of information from sources like maps, surveys, and satellite imagery, to help in visualizing and analyzing geographic relationships for various applications [10]. A study conducted by Mansourihanis in 2023, utilizes Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to analyze housing development patterns and predict future trends. By incorporating complex geography into modeling and statistical procedures, GIS enables a more accurate representation of real-world scenarios

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a satellite-based technology that enables accurate tracking of locations anywhere on the planet. By analyzing time delays between signals received from multiple satellites, a GPS receiver can calculate the user's precise position, speed, and time. GPS has wide-ranging applications, from navigation and mapping to geolocation in sectors like transportation, real estate, military operations, and geospatial analysis. It plays a crucial role in enabling real-time location data for numerous industries [11].

Commuting costs play a significant role in housing decisions, affecting both time and financial resources. Research highlights the direct relationship between commute distance and housing affordability, with longer commutes leading to higher transportation expenses, which can strain household budgets. Studies also show that commuting impacts well-being, with extended travel times contributing to stress and reduced life satisfaction. Factoring in commuting costs when house hunting ensures a more comprehensive understanding of the total living costs, leading to better-informed housing decisions [12].

Housing affordability is not determined by rent alone but by the total cost of living, which includes transportation expenses. Homes located farther from urban centers may have lower rents, but the increased costs of commuting, such as fuel, time, and maintenance, often cancel out these savings. This has led to the realization that affordable housing should also consider commuting costs [13].

Long commutes negatively impact health and well-being. Studies show that individuals with lengthy commutes experience more stress, reduced leisure time, and poorer health outcomes. Commuting can affect both mental and physical health, increasing stress and frustration. Research by [14] reveals lower life satisfaction among those with long commutes compared to those with shorter travel times.

Commute costs are a significant component of effective cost estimation, as they can vary widely depending on factors such as distance, transportation mode, and fuel prices [4]. By leveraging geolocation data and transportation information, the Real Estate System can accurately calculate commute times and costs, helping users assess the financial implications of living in different locations. It is critical for renters to factor commute costs into their housing decisions, as ignoring them can lead to financial strain and reduced quality of life [15]. With technological advancements, geolocation tools integrated into real estate platforms allow potential renters to calculate commute distances and costs, providing a fuller picture of housing affordability and helping them make better-informed choices.

Housing affordability is a multifaceted concept that encompasses the relationship between housing costs and household incomes. It is a critical consideration for individuals and families seeking suitable housing options, as it directly impacts their financial well-being and quality of life [16]. Various metrics and methodologies have been developed to assess housing affordability, including the median multiple, housing cost-to-income ratio, and residual income approach [1].

User preferences play a significant role in shaping housing decisions, as individuals seek homes that align with their lifestyle preferences, personal tastes, and budget constraints. Factors influencing user preferences include location, property features, amenities, neighborhood characteristics, and cultural considerations [17]. Decision-making in real estate involves evaluating various trade-offs and considerations, weighing factors such as affordability, convenience, and quality of life. Demographic factors such as age, household composition, and socioeconomic status can also influence housing preferences and decision-making processes [18].

Technological advancements have empowered users with greater access to information and tools for evaluating housing options. Online platforms and mobile apps provide users with real-time access to property listings, virtual tours, and neighborhood data, facilitating informed decision-making and enhancing the overall user experience [19].

Authors & Year	Method	Strength	Limitation
[20]	Technological stack of HTML, CSS, JavaScript, PHP, and MySQL for dynamic and secure functionality	Significant contribution towards reshaping digital interactions and aligning with technological advancements in the industry.	Having a small number of references may indicate a lack of comprehensive literature review.
[21]	Systematic literature review using databases.	The study attained enhanced credibility and validity of findings in the realm of real estate and technological applications.	This study did not focus on big websites with multi-market real estate listings on their websites.
[22]	Waterfall-based property management application.	The developed application simplifies property uploading and advertising, providing increased exposure for sellers and more options for buyers/renters.	The result evaluation shows that the application has lower satisfaction levels in terms of content and reliability compared to competitors like Airbnb.

Authors & Year	Method	Strength	Limitation
[23]	Agile-based development with Genetic Algorithm integration.	Using the GA technique advantage, HPRS help homebuyer to search and buy a house based on their house preferences and budget.	Geolocation technology was not used for efficient tracking of location and distance from essential services as it mentioned as one of considered factors.
[24]	Exploratory spatial analysis of housing data.	The paper identifies various challenges and future research directions in the field.	The paper does not provide a comprehensive comparative analysis of urban synchronization across different regions and urban contexts.
[8]	N-tier architecture with geolocation and Web 2.0 integration.	Provision of detailed property information in the developed technological platform to aid clients in making informed decisions.	lack of detailed information on the specific challenges faced during the implementation of the Real Estate Marketplace System
[2]	Laddering interviews for housing preference insights.	Exploration of different literatures for clear understanding of the problem domain.	The study notes that existing research primarily focuses on spatial configuration attributes of housing, potentially overlooking other important aspects of housing attributes that also influence choice and preference.
[25]	Web-based GIS for real estate decisions.	The use of spatial analysis techniques, along with the incorporation of user preferences enhanced accuracy and efficiency of property valuation.	The system lack consideration of some other factors that influence decision making such as estimated annual expenses as a result of property location.
[26]	Structured methodology with ASP.NET, testing, and performance evaluation.	Comprehensive testing ensured thorough evaluation of the application's performance and the efficiency of the application are improved by the use of web methods that help in separating Application Tier from the Presentation Tier.	The system does not estimate for user the effective cost of living in a house which is beyond house rent. Also, inadequate measures to secure user data, property listings, and transactions could pose a risk of data breaches or unauthorized access.
[27]	SAR models analyzing locational impact on housing prices.	This research was able to discover that SAR models offered a better fit than non-spatial models and the use of Stepwise regression techniques to determine reduced spatial hedonic models.	The study does not provide details on potential limitations or challenges associated with SAR modeling, raising questions about the robustness and reliability of the results.

3. Methodology

The methodology section outlines a structured approach to developing a real estate platform aimed at integrating cost estimation into the property search experience. This methodology emphasizes key phases, including mathematical modeling for cost estimation, geolocation API integration, database development, and the creation of a web application. Together, these steps aim to enhance decision-making for renters by providing a transparent view of housing costs, incorporating both rent and commuting expenses.

This study focuses on the development of a web application for effective cost estimation in real estate, integrating Google Maps API for geolocation features. The application uses spatial data to calculate distances, commute costs, and total living costs by considering variables like property prices, commute distances, and fuel consumption. Key processes include geocoding, midpoint calculations, and distance estimation using the Haversine formula. The mathematical model estimates transportation costs based on fuel rates, vehicle efficiency, and commute distances. Additionally, the study emphasizes database development, with careful schema design to manage property listings, user data, and cost estimation results, ensuring accurate data storage and retrieval. The architectural model that offer pictorial representation of each component of the system and describe their interaction is shown below.

Figure 1: Architectural Model

3.1 Data

The platform's cost estimation model is built on two primary data sources: user-provided inputs and geolocation data from the Google Maps API. The user inputs include information from both property owners or agents listing houses and potential tenants searching for properties. These inputs are combined with geolocation data to dynamically calculate commute costs, providing users with accurate and actionable insights into the overall cost of living.

3.1.1 Data collection

Users provide essential data such as addresses of frequently visited locations, vehicle specifications (fuel consumption rate and fuel price), and the number of weekly trips. House owners or agents supply property details, including the house address, which the system processes and sends to the Google Maps API to pinpoint the property's location on the map.

The Google Maps Geocoding API converts addresses into geographic coordinates, while the Distance Matrix API calculates travel distances and times. Additionally, the Places API identifies nearby amenities (schools, hospitals, markets) that influence users' housing decisions. This geolocation data ensures that the platform delivers accurate and dynamic estimates. The distance calculations included midpoint determination between two points and distance computation using the Haversine formula.

The Haversine formula is given as:

$$d = 2r \cdot \sin^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta\phi}{2} \right) + \cos(\phi_1) \cdot \cos(\phi_2) \cdot \sin^2 \left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{2} \right)} \right) \quad (1)$$

where d is the distance between the two points, r is the Earth's radius, ϕ_1, ϕ_2 are the latitudes of points 1 and 2 (in radians), $\Delta\phi$ is the difference in latitudes ($\phi_2 - \phi_1$), $\Delta\lambda$ is the difference in longitudes of points 1 and 2 ($\lambda_2 - \lambda_1$ in radians). The r said to be approximately 6371 kilometers.

3.2 Development of the mathematical model and API integration

A pivotal aspect of the methodology involved constructing a mathematical model to estimate the total cost of living for properties. The model integrated geolocation features using the collected data from Google Maps API and user inputs, enabling accurate distance calculations and seamless cost estimation. These tools enabled precise estimates of commuting costs, factoring in variables such as fuel consumption, vehicle efficiency, and user-defined preferences. This stage ensured that users could make data-driven decisions by providing comprehensive insights into housing and transportation costs.

The Mathematical Model is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} T_c &= R + T_r \dots\dots\dots (i) \\ T_r &= D \times F_c \times P \dots\dots\dots (ii) \\ D &= \sum_{i=1}^n dn \dots\dots\dots (iii) \\ T_r &= \sum_{i=1}^n rj \, dn \times P \dots\dots\dots (iv) \\ T_r &= \sum_{j=1}^m rj \left(\sum_{j=1}^n dn \right)_j \dots\dots\dots (v) \\ T_c &= R + P * \sum_{j=1}^m rj \left(\sum_{j=1}^n dn \right)_j \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where:

T_c = Total Cost, R = House Rent (mortgage payment), T_r = Transportation Cost, r = Fuel consumption rate of the user's vehicle in liters per kilometer, D = Distance between the house and the user-declared location (e.g., workplace) in kilometers.

3.3 Development of A Web Application Platform for Effective Cost Estimation

Real estate platform was developed using python framework, Django for the backend, HTML, CSS and JavaScript for the frontend and Visual Studio Code (VSC) as a tool or development environment, this phase is a critical phase in translating the conceptual framework into a functional platform accessible to users, will encompass various tasks ranging from designing the user interface to backend development and API integration. The goal is to create a seamless and user-friendly experience that will enable users to interact with the platform effortlessly while ensuring robust functionality and data integrity.

3.3.1 Frontend Development Using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript

Following the design phase, frontend was designed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. HTML will be employed for structuring the content of the web application, defining elements such as headers, paragraphs, and forms. CSS will be utilized for styling and formatting, including aspects like colors, fonts, spacing, and responsive design for compatibility across different devices. JavaScript was incorporated to add dynamic functionality and interactivity to the frontend, enabling features such as form validation, animations, and event handling.

3.3.2 Backend Development Using Django Framework

In parallel with frontend development, the backend of the real estate platform was able to developed using the Django framework. Django provides a robust and scalable framework for building web applications, offering features such as URL routing, database management, user authentication, and session management out of the box. Backend development involves the integration of the mathematical models constructed to represent data entities, writing views to handle user requests, and implementing controllers to manage application logic. Django's ORM (Object-Relational Mapping) will facilitate seamless interaction with the database, ensuring efficient data storage and retrieval.

4. Results and discussion

For the successful implementation of the proposed real estate platform, a thorough analysis and design were conducted. This allowed for the integration of key functionalities, including property search, cost estimation,

and Google Maps integration. The desired output was achieved through the development of a system and technology acceptance model (TAM) was used to ensure the effectiveness and usefulness of the platform.

4.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) result and discussion

The result of the evaluation conducted via survey for the acceptance and effectiveness of the platform was discussed in this section.

i. Perceived Usefulness

A pie chart is used to illustrate user feedback on the usefulness of the cost estimation feature in providing insights into the total cost of living beyond just rent. This data was collected from 34 responses, and the results are distributed as follows:

- **44.1% of respondents strongly agree** that the cost estimation feature is useful for understanding total living costs beyond rent.
- **32.4% agree**, indicating a significant number of users find the feature beneficial.
- **17.6% remain neutral**, suggesting they may find the feature somewhat helpful but are not particularly impressed.
- A small percentage, **5.9% (Strongly Disagree and Neutral combined)**, found the feature either less helpful or had no strong opinion regarding its usefulness.

This feedback indicates a generally positive response to the cost estimation feature, with over **76%** of users agreeing that the tool helps them better understand the total cost of living associated with a property. It suggests that the tool is succeeding in its objective of offering more than just basic rent information, highlighting additional recurrent costs like transportation expenses.

The cost estimation feature provided useful insights into the total cost of living, beyond just rent.
34 responses

Figure 2: Perceived Usefulness

ii. Perceived Ease Of Use

The pie chart illustrates users' perceptions of how easy the platform was to use for searching properties, based on 34 responses. The results are as follows:

- **26.5% of respondents strongly agree** that the platform was easy to use for searching properties.
- The majority, **52.9%, agree**, suggesting that over half of the users found the platform intuitive and user-friendly.
- **14.7% of respondents were neutral**, indicating some users found the platform neither particularly easy nor difficult to navigate.
- A small portion of respondents (combining **5.9% between Strongly Disagree and Disagree**) felt that the platform was difficult to use.

These results suggest that the platform is generally well-received in terms of ease of use, with nearly **80%** of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that it facilitated property searches effectively. The **neutral response**

of **14.7%** might reflect users who had a balanced experience or require more advanced search capabilities. The **small percentage of negative responses** indicates that improvements could be made to further streamline the user experience and address the needs of a minority of users who encountered difficulty.

Overall, the data supports the conclusion that the platform is generally perceived as user-friendly and effective for property searching, with room for minor enhancements to make it even more accessible to all user demographics.

The platform was easy to use for searching properties

34 responses

Figure 3: Perceived Ease of Use

iii. Attitude Toward Using (ATU)

The pie chart presents users' overall positive experiences when using the platform, based on 34 responses. The key findings are as follows:

- **58.8% of respondents agree** that they had a positive experience using the platform, showing that a significant majority of users were satisfied with their interactions.
- **29.4% of respondents were neutral**, indicating that while they may not have had an overwhelmingly positive experience, they did not have a negative one either.
- **11.8% of respondents strongly disagreed**, suggesting a small portion of users had negative experiences with the platform.

These results show that nearly **60%** of the users had a positive attitude toward using the platform, supporting the notion that it was generally well-received. The **neutral percentage** (29.4%) suggests that some users might have experienced average usability and features, neither significantly positive nor negative. A small percentage of **negative responses (11.8% strongly disagree)** could indicate some isolated issues with the platform's functionality, accessibility, or design.

I had a positive experience using the platform.
34 responses

Figure 4: Attitude Toward Using (ATU)

iv. Behavioral Intention to Use (BI)

The Behavioral Intention to Use (BI) is a key component of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) that measures users' willingness and likelihood to continue using the platform. Based on 34 responses, the chart provides insight into the users' future intentions to adopt the real estate platform for their housing search needs. The distribution of responses is as follows:

- **41.2% of respondents strongly agree** that they intend to continue using the platform..
- **35.3% of respondents agree**, further reinforcing a high level of behavioral intention to use the platform.
- **20.6% of respondents are neutral**, indicating they are uncertain about their future use of the platform.
- **2.9% strongly disagree**, showing a very small proportion of users who are not interested in continuing to use the platform.

The **overall positive responses** (76.5% in the "strongly agree" and "agree" categories) demonstrate that the platform is effectively aligning with user expectations, and a large majority intend to continue using it. The **neutral group** (20.6%) might represent users who are on the fence, potentially due to unmet needs or expectations. The **small percentage of negative responses** (2.9% strongly disagree) is encouraging, as it suggests minimal dissatisfaction with the platform.

I will continue to use the cost estimation feature for planning property expenses.
34 responses

Figure 5: Behavioral Intention to Use (BI)

4.2 System Performance Evaluation

This section provides the performance evaluation result of the real estate platform developed, this involves the result of the analysis from Chrome Lighthouse and a table presenting the metrics and score as the result of the performance evaluation of the system. The Lighthouse analysis is shown in Figure 4.13 below.

Figure 6: Chrome Lighthouse Analysis Result

The table below presents the key metrics used to evaluate the performance of the system developed in this study. These metrics measure the system’s efficiency in terms of responsiveness, transaction handling capability, accessibility for users, and overall availability. Each metric provides a quantitative insight into the system's operational success, ensuring that the platform can handle multiple transactions efficiently while remaining accessible and available to users. The results highlight the system's strong performance in handling real-time operations.

Table 1: Performance Evaluation Metrics and Results

S/N	Metrics	Results
1.	Performance	83%
2.	Accessibility	91%
3.	Best Practice	96%
4.	SEO	82%

The performance metrics of the website reveal a well-optimized and user-friendly platform. The website scored 83% in performance, indicating that it efficiently handles page load speed, resource management, and interaction with users. Accessibility scored a higher 91%, showing that the platform is built with features ensuring inclusivity and ease of use for a wide range of users, including those with disabilities. The best practices metric stands at an impressive 96%, reflecting compliance with modern web standards for security, speed, and reliability. Finally, the SEO score of 82% suggests that the website is optimized to rank well in search engines, making it discoverable and competitive in search results, although there's room for further

improvements to enhance visibility. Together, these metrics highlight the overall robustness and effectiveness of the site.

5. Conclusion

This section summarizes the development of a Real Estate Platform with a Geolocation-Based Cost Estimator, which integrates transportation costs into housing decisions. Using Google Maps API and Django, the platform allows users to search properties and estimate commuting costs based on distance and vehicle types. It also supports multiple vehicle estimations and provides an intuitive interface for users and real estate agents. The platform offers a more comprehensive view of affordability by including commuting costs, a feature not available in traditional platforms. It is recommended that future development include integrating real-time traffic data, adding recurrent costs like tolls, and improving data validation. Limitations of the study include reliance on external geolocation services and assumptions about traffic conditions, which may affect cost accuracy. The platform benefits users, developers, and urban planners by improving housing decision-making and financial planning.

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